

Thiohydrazide as complexing agents. Part-IV. Complexes of nickel-, copper-, zinc-, cadmium- and mercury(II) with phenyl and *p*-anisidyl thiohydrazides

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Complexes of some bivalent metal ions with phenylthiohydrazide (pthH) and *p*-anisidylthiohydrazide (pathH) of the general formula, ML_2 ($M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}$ or Pb^{II} and $LH = pthH$ or $pathH$), $[M(LH)Cl_2]$ ($M = Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}$ or Hg^{II} and $LH = pthH$ or $pathH$) and $[Ni(LH)_2]X_2$ ($LH = pthH$ or $pathH$) and $X = Cl^-$ or $1/2 SO_4^{2-}$ have been prepared and characterised.

In continuation of our studies on metal complexes of thiohydrazides^{1,2} and thiohydrazones³, we report herein the preparation and characterisation of complexes of bivalent Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Hg and Pb with phenylthiohydrazide (pthH) and *p*-anisidylthiohydrazide (pathH). The complexes of salicylthiohydrazide were formed by coordination of deprotonated phenolic OH and thione sulfur. Here, pthH and pathH form neutral bis-chelates $[ML_2]$ from deprotonated thiol sulfur and hydrazide NH_2 nitrogen.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses indicate the formation of $[ML_2]$ type of complexes with pthH and pathH in neutral medium. In acidic solution (pH < 3) these ligands coordinate as neutral molecule (thione form) and form dihalo complexes $[M(LH)Cl_2]$ with Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} or Hg^{II} and bischelated complex salts $[Ni(LH)_2]X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$ or $1/2 SO_4^{2-}$).

The neutral bis-chelates ML_2 as well as dichloro complexes $[M(LH)Cl_2]$ are insoluble in water but dissolve in DMF. In DMF solution, the dihalo complexes show negligible electric conductance values ($6-15 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) at room temperature (30°), indicating their non-ionic character⁴. The DMF solution of $[Ni(LH)_2]Cl_2$ shows molar conductance value $126-138 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ which indicates that chloride ions are ionic in nature⁴.

The complexes $[NiL_2]$ ($LH = pthH$ or $pathH$) as well as $[Ni(LH)_2]X_2$ are diamagnetic and therefore possess four-coordinated square-planar structure⁵. The copper(II) complexes show normal magnetic moment value (1.80–1.87 B.M.) indicating that the complexes are magnetically dilute⁶. The electronic absorption spectra of pthH show

bands at 240 and 290 nm while pathH displays bands at 230 and 275 nm attributable to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions respectively. The ethanolic (or DMF) solutions of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes display very strong absorption below 380 nm attributable to charge transfer transition. The DMF solution of $[NiL_2]$, $[Ni(LH)_2]X_2$, $[Cu(LH)Cl_2]$ or $[CuL_2]$ does not display distinct band in the visible region but reflectance spectra of the complexes reveal one or two medium bands or shoulder in the visible region due to ligand field transitions. The reflectance band of $[NiL_2]$ ($LH = pthH$ or $pathH$) at 430–440 nm is assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transition in planar field. The shoulder near 400 and 500 nm of planar $[Ni(LH)_2]Cl_2$ (pthH or pathH) are assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{3g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively⁷. The electronic reflectance spectra of the dichloro complexes $[Cu(LH)Cl_2]$ ($LH = pthH$ or $pathH$) display shoulder near 400 nm and a broad and strong asymmetric band at 600–800 nm. The former band can be assigned to charge transfer type whereas the latter one can be attributed to a combination of $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ transitions in idealised tetragonal field⁸.

From stoichiometry and other physicochemical evidences, four-coordinated tetrahedral geometry is suggested for Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes⁹.

The pmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$) of *p*-anisidylthiohydrazide shows methoxy proton signal at δ 3.75 (3H, s, CH_3). The downfield shift of methyl proton in the free ligand is due to deshielding arising from electron-withdrawing effect of highly electronegative oxygen atom. The methoxy proton signal of the ligand is not further affected on coordination. The terminal NH_2 proton signal is observed as a broad

band at δ 4.45 (2H). The spectra of $[M(\text{path})_2]$ ($M = \text{Zn}$ or Ni) show NH_2 signal at δ 5.46 but methoxy proton signals was not affected appreciably. The downfield shifting of NH_2 proton signal confirmed the coordination of terminal hydrazide NH_2 nitrogen to the metal atom. The hydrazide NH proton signal of the ligand was observed at δ 8.5 as broad and weak band. Besides NH proton signal observed at δ 7.91 can be attributable to SH proton, which indicates the presence of a little thiol tautomer of thioamide group ($-\text{CS}-\text{NH}-$). The absence of SH and NH proton signals in the spectra of bischelate $[\text{Ni}(\text{path})_2]$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{path})_2]$ supports coordination of the ligand through deprotonated thiol sulphur. The phenyl ring proton of the ligand located at *ortho* to methoxy group shows signal at δ 6.71 and 6.81 (2H, d) which is not affected in the complexes. The phenyl proton of the ligand located *ortho* to thioamide group shows further downfield shift and is observed at δ 7.55 and 7.65 (2H, d). In complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{path})_2]$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{path})_2]$ these proton signals are observed at δ 7.68 and 7.78 (4H, d). The downfield shift is attributed to coordination of adjacent sulphur atom with metal.

The pmr spectrum (CDCl_3) of phenylthiohydrazide shows phenyl ring proton signals as multiplet at δ (CDCl_3) 6.75–6.95 (3H, m) and 7.55–7.65 (2H, d, protons adjacent to thiohydrazide group). The NH_2 proton signal is observed at δ 4.52 (2H, br) and the NH proton at δ 8.45. A sharp signal at δ 7.32 (SH) indicates some thiol tautomer in CDCl_3 . The SH and NH proton signals are absent in $\text{Ni}(\text{pth})_2$, indicating the bonding of the ligand through deprotonated thiol sulphur. The signals for phenyl protons adjacent to thioamide group suffer downfield shift and are observed at δ 7.75 and 7.85 (4H, d) due to coordination of the ligand. The NH_2 proton signal of $\text{Ni}(\text{pth})_2$ is observed at δ 5.35 (4H, s br). The downfield shift of NH_2 proton signal is attributed to coordination of the terminal NH_2 nitrogen through metal atom.

In ir spectra, medium band at 3220 (pthH) and 3248 cm^{-1} (pathH) attributable to NH_2 stretch of the free ligand is shifted to lower frequencies by 40–125 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating the coordination of hydrazine (NH_2) nitrogen with the metal atom¹⁰. The absence of band near 2500–2650 cm^{-1} in the free ligand indicates the presence of only thione tautomer in solid state.

The $\delta_{\text{NH}_2} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ band of the ligands is observed at 1598 for pthH and 1603 cm^{-1} for pathH. In the complexes, this band is not affected appreciably and is observed at 1582–1610 cm^{-1} . These ligands possess potential thioamide group^{11,12}. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the ligands are raised to higher frequencies in the complexes indicating coordination of thioamide group to the metal atoms. The

thioamide band IV is shifted to lower frequencies by 120–160 cm^{-1} in the neutral bis-chelates while it is not affected in the complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2]\text{X}_2$. A large red-shift of thioamide band IV in ML_2 type of complexes suggests the bonding^{12,13} of sulphur in thiol form on deprotonation. In far-infrared region the new bands observed at 485–345 and 365–320 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to M–N and M–S stretching vibrations¹⁴.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported in literature². Metal salts and chemicals used were either of E. Merck extra pure or B.D.H. of A.R. quality.

$[\text{ML}_2]$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}, \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{LH} = \text{pthH}$ or pathH): An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal acetate (0.01 mol) in 50% ethanol (100 ml) was treated with an excess of hot ethanolic solution (60 ml) of the ligand (0.03 mol) with stirring when neutral bis-chelates separated out gradually. The products were digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 . The copper(II) complexes were filtered without digestion as Cu^{II} gets reduced slowly by the ligand in solution (yield is almost quantitative).

$[\text{M}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2]$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ or Hg^{II} and $\text{LH} = \text{pthH}$ or pathH): An ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (0.01 mol in 60 ml) and the ligand (0.01 mol in 30 ml) was stirred when the dichloro complexes separated out gradually. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above (yield 80%).

$[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{LH} = \text{pthH}$ or pathH , and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$): These complexes were prepared as above using 1 : 2 molar ratio of ligand-metal and pH was adjusted to 2–3 by adding a few drops of appropriate acid. For preparation of the complex sulphate, an aqueous solution of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used (yield 80%).

The magnetic moment was taken at 305 K and the values were calculated after making correction for TIP contribution. The electronic or reflectance spectra were recorded on Hilger and Watt H700 spectrophotometer using MgCO_3 as standard and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60 instrument (60 MHz). Ir spectra and electrical conductivity were measured as reported earlier¹.

References

1. U. Kumari, C. P. Singh and L. K. Mishra. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 255; B. N. Keshari and L. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 883; K. Das, U. S. Prasad, A. K. Dubey and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 497; L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1198.
2. A. Kumar, A. K. Jha, N. Majumdar, S. N. Yadav and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 485; K. A. Jensen and C. Pederson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, **15**, 1097.

Note

3. A. Kumar, A. K. Jha, N. Majumdar, S. N. Yadav and L. K. Mishra, *Bull. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 1996, **16C**, 89, 95.
4. M. J. Geary, *Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **7**, 81; J. V. Quagliano, J. Fujita, G. Fraz, D. T. Phillips and S. Y. Tyree, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
5. S. I. Shupak, E. Billing R. J. H. Clark, R. Williams and H. B. Gray, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 4595.
6. M. Kato, H. B. Jonassen and J. C. Fanning, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 99.
7. A. Albert and E. Spinner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1221, 1237; G. Peyronel, G. C. Pellacani and A. Pignedoli, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 627; W. Manch and W. C. Fernelius, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 192.
8. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1984.
9. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry A Comprehensive Text", Interscience, New York, 1988.
10. J. N. Quagliano, G. V. Svatos and B. C. Curran, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 429.
11. M. K. Das, M. Nath and J. J. Zuckerman, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **21**, 49, C. N. R. Rao, R. Venkataraghavan and T. R. Kasturi, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **82**, 36.
12. R. D. Bereman, D. M. Baird, L. Bordner and J. Dorfman, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 25.
13. J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency, Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971.
14. D. M. Adams, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967; M. Akbar Ali, S. E. Livingstone and D. J. Phillips, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 119, 493.